

Defensive Bioweapons-related Research: The New Threat of Mutually Assured Destruction

In a world haunted by the specter of nuclear weapons, defensive bioweapons-related research has quietly emerged as the next existential threat. Unlike nuclear arms, where research, development, and peaceful uses are clearly distinguishable, bioweapons-related research operates in a murky dual-use realm. Laboratories engaged in ostensibly civilian research might quickly pivot to projects with military applications, often using the same facilities and equipment. A story first reported in the Washington Post showed Russia was revitalizing its old bioweapon site near Moscow, ostensibly for defensive purposes. Meanwhile China ramps up research on the deadly Nipah virus—a pathogen with a 70% fatality rate but no likely public health threat to China—it is clear that the global balance of power may soon hinge on this new form of deterrence. And just like nuclear weapons in the 1960s, bioweapons-related research is reaching a dangerous stage where mutual destruction is all but inevitable.

The parallels between the current moment and the Cold War are striking. In 1962, Secretary of Defense Robert McNamara proposed a "no-cities" approach to nuclear war, arguing that the United States should target military forces rather than civilian populations if the Soviet Union attacked NATO. The backlash was immediate, as critics feared that a more "limited" approach to nuclear warfare might make the use of such weapons more likely. McNamara quickly pivoted to emphasize "assured destruction," a strategy that rested on the mutual certainty of devastating retaliation, effectively deterring any rational actor from initiating a nuclear war. It was a doctrine built on fear, but it held the peace through the Cold War. Today, the world faces a similar crossroads with bioweapons-related research, yet the risks are largely unseen and harder to control.

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Unlike nuclear weapons, bioweapons could be developed under the guise of legitimate research. This is evident in the surge of high-containment labs, including BSL-4 facilities, which handle the deadliest pathogens. A 2023 report, *High Consequence Bio Labs: Growing Risks and Lagging Governance*, revealed a COVID-inspired proliferation of such labs worldwide: 26 in Europe, 20 in Asia, 15 in North America, and others in Oceania, Africa, and South America. Many of these labs are situated in urban centers, increasing the risks of accidental or intentional releases. Alarmingly, several of these facilities are in politically unstable regions, raising questions about the control and oversight of their research. A biosafety or biosecurity incident in any of these labs could have consequences as dire as a nuclear exchange.

Moreover, unlike nuclear technologies, where missile silos and enrichment facilities offer clear signals of intent, the nature of bioweapon-related research makes it nearly impossible to distinguish between defensive research and offensive development. This ambiguity is evident in recent controversies in the United States. One of the world's leading coronavirus researchers, who according to the McCullough Foundation has received over \$282 million in federal funding, including from the Department of Defense, succeeded in blocking the release of thousands of pages of documents detailing how that money was used. The secrecy surrounding such research, especially when it involves pathogens with pandemic potential, underscores the difficulty in assessing whether such work is truly aimed at public health or harbors more sinister intentions.

The situation is compounded by the alarming advances in biotechnology. Genome editing, immune epitope targeting, and synthetic biology have made it possible to manipulate pathogens in ways that were unthinkable just a few decades ago. Today, genes can be synthesized with technology adapted from a high-end office laser-printer. Scientists can now engineer viruses to be more infectious, to spread without symptoms, or to possess targeted lethality—all while maintaining control over case fatality rates. This new reality makes bioweapons research as dangerous as the nuclear arms race became with the development of intercontinental ballistic missiles, submarine-launched ballistic missiles, and multiple independently targetable reentry vehicles. These three

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advancements made nuclear mutual destruction inescapable, and now we face a similar turning point with bioweapons.

The COVID-19 pandemic offers a stark warning about the potential for unintended consequences, even when bioweapons-related research is likely defensive. If one begins from the possibility that SARS-CoV-2 originated from a US-China cooperative research effort with civilian intent — whether for vaccine development or other countermeasures—the scale of the damage in both countries proves that such research can backfire catastrophically. The devastation wrought by COVID-19 demonstrated the inherent unpredictability of pathogens, which can evolve and spread in ways that even the best-prepared researchers cannot anticipate. The blowback risk from bioweapons-related defensive research is immense, and yet, unlike during the nuclear era, the world's countermeasures remain woefully inadequate.

Despite the rapid development of COVID-19 vaccines, their limitations have been glaring. They have not proven as effective or as safe as initially hoped, and the reasons remain elusive. This gap between our ability to engineer deadly pathogens and our capacity to control them is deeply troubling. We now have more expertise in creating viruses that could kill millions than we do in effectively treating those who become infected. The technological imbalance is dangerous, making it clear that the world's understanding of bioweapons has reached a critical stage that demands urgent action.

We must recognize that bioweapons research has entered the same high-stakes phase that nuclear technology did during the Cold War. As a result, the world needs to adopt a doctrine of biological deterrence akin to mutually assured destruction. This would require new international agreements, with the weight of law, to halt the proliferation of high-risk bioresearch and to establish

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transparency measures for existing labs. Just as nuclear arms treaties helped to prevent the worst outcomes of the Cold War, global regulation of bioweapon research could avert a catastrophic future.

It is time for world leaders to acknowledge the peril and work together to create a framework that can contain it. The history of nuclear deterrence offers a template: a clear acknowledgment of the threat, a shared understanding that any use would be disastrous for all, and rigorous verification mechanisms to ensure compliance. **Amending the Biological Weapons Treaty could be an important starting point.** Anything less invites a future where bioweapons become a central tool of global conflict, where accidents or rogue actors can unleash pathogens that humanity is unprepared to combat.

The stakes are immense. As we have seen with COVID-19, the next pandemic could be far worse, especially if it is engineered with malign intent. The world cannot afford to repeat the mistakes of the nuclear arms race, waiting for disaster before taking action. By establishing a global doctrine of biological deterrence and curbing the proliferation of bioweapons-related research, we can avert a future where mutual destruction by disease becomes a grim reality.

Dr. Quay has testified before Congress on the origin of the COVID-19 virus and measures to prevent a future viral pandemic.